

Geophysical sensing using Jones matrices extracted from submarine optical cable transceivers carrying live traffic

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We present a general and rigorous theoretical framework for analyzing polarization evolution in optical fibers in the presence of random polarization coupling. This framework enables the extraction of all available information about external perturbations from the Jones matrix retrieved by a coherent receiver during normal operation without compromising the privacy of the data. We apply the theory to telemetry data collected from commercial coherent transponders deployed on both ends of two links that connect Catania, Italy, to Tel Aviv and Haifa, Israel, belonging to Sparkle's MedNautilus undersea fiber-optic system. The dataset comprises Jones matrices describing the input–output polarization transformations of the fiber. By comparing the Jones matrices of counter-propagating signals transmitted through two fibers sharing the same cable, we demonstrate that the sensing information encoded in the polarization changes is unaffected by random polarization coupling. This is achieved by comparing spectrograms of the perturbation-induced variations of the rotation vectors derived from the Jones matrices. Finally, we validate the capability of the method to detect seismic events by analyzing data from four receivers carrying live-traffic during the Mw 5.8 earthquake that struck the Dodecanese Islands on June 2, 2025, at 23:17:27.8 UTC.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Long-haul optical communication systems that are deployed nowadays use coherent detection and digital signal processing (DSP) technology. Coherent systems need to reconstruct for their operation the polarization changes that light undergoes during its journey [1]. These polarization changes are described by a matrix, known as the Jones matrix, which is therefore sensitive to all perturbations that act on the optical fiber along its path. This matrix can be extracted, with minimal modifications to the transponder hardware, from coherent optical communication systems during their normal operation, without altering the data flow in any way. In addition, as no information on the transmitted data can be obtained from the Jones matrix, one can ensure that its extraction from the receiver does not compromise traffic privacy. The analysis of a subset of information that can be extracted from the Jones matrix, duly processed, has shown impressive sensing capabilities. For example, the analysis of

the output polarization that corresponds to a linear polarization at input has shown its potential for detecting various environmental perturbations. In ref. [2], a number of earthquakes that occurred near the Curie undersea optical cable, which connects Los Angeles, California, to Valparaiso, Chile, were detected. Additionally, minuscule ultra-low frequency modulations of the hydrostatic pressure acting on the cable were revealed, which resulted from ocean swells and from semidiurnal modulations originating from ocean tides in the region close to the Los Angeles terminal of the cable [3, 4].

In this paper, we develop the most general theoretical framework for extracting geophysical sensing information from the temporal variations of the polarization in undersea optical fibers. Building on a rigorous analysis of the spatial evolution of the Jones matrix of a fiber link in the presence of random polarization coupling, we devise a sensing method that surpasses those based on a single input polarization utilized in [2, 3]. By captur-

ing the aggregate effect of perturbations along the entire cable light-path, our method achieves unprecedented sensitivity in detecting a wide range of events. We validate our approach using data from the Sparkle's MedNautilus undersea fiber-optic system depicted in Fig. 1 and illustrate its effectiveness by analyzing the time-dependent polarization changes that occurred during a recent earthquake in the Eastern Mediterranean, demonstrating that coherent receivers can serve as effective seismic sensors.

Fig. 1. Map of the Med Nautilus transmission system. The two ovals indicate the Catania–Haifa and the Catania–Tel Aviv links of interest in this study. The cable paths are shown schematically and do not reflect their precise locations. The star indicates the epicenter of an earthquake of magnitude $M_w = 5.8$ that took place on June 2, 2025 at 23:17:27.8 UTC.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Let us first describe the theoretical background at the basis of the sensing technique. In an ideal lossless fiber, the optical field evolves following a unitary evolution described by the z dependent unitary matrix \mathbf{U} that maps the two complex-valued scalar orthogonal components of the transmitted optical field at the fiber input with those at position z along the fiber. At the output $z = L$ of a transmission system of length L employing coherent detection, the coherent optical receiver retrieves the Jones matrix in order to compensate for linear propagation effects. In a real fiber link, polarization dependent loss breaks the unitary nature of the transmission. Since, however, polarization dependent loss is in general small, not exceeding fractions of dB over thousands of kilometers long fibers, it is always possible to obtain a good estimate of the unitary matrix \mathbf{U} by applying a singular-value decomposition to the transmission matrix obtained from the coherent receiver, and taking the unitary part of the result [5]. We will implicitly assume in the following that \mathbf{U} is z dependent, and that its value at $z = L$ is the unitary matrix detected by the receiver.

The Jones matrix of an optical link can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{U} = \exp \left[-\frac{i}{2} \varphi_0(t) \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \vec{\varphi}(t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right], \quad (1)$$

where the dot symbol denotes scalar product between vectors, $\mathbb{1}$ is the identity matrix and $\vec{\sigma}$ is a Pauli vector defined as $\vec{\sigma} = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3]$, with σ_k the Pauli matrices defined as [6]

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (1), $\varphi_0(t)$ is the polarization averaged phase and $\vec{\varphi}(t)$ is the polarization rotation vector, which owes its name to the property that the input-output transformation corresponds in Stokes space to a rotation represented by $\vec{\varphi}(t)$ [6]. Once again, like for \mathbf{U} , these quantities depend on the position z along the fiber and their values at $z = L$ characterize the unitary matrix measured at the receiver. The equation describing the evolution of \mathbf{U} is

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}}{dz} = -\frac{i}{2} \left[\beta_0(z, t) \mathbb{1} + \vec{\beta}(z, t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right] \mathbf{U}, \quad (3)$$

where $\beta_0(z)$ is the polarization averaged wave-vector and $\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ is the fiber birefringence. In the ideal case, $\beta_0(z, t)$ and $\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ are the sum of static components and time dependent components, which will be the result of the perturbations. Even with perfect transponder stability and in the absence of other spurious effects, long-term perturbations may cause the polarization state to drift across the entire polarization space, pushing the sensor outside its linear range. Although this typically occurs only over very long timescales, on the order of many hours, it nevertheless requires compensation. For this purpose, it is convenient to decompose $\beta_0(z, t)$ and $\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ in quasi static components, which we assume varying over a long time scale T , and faster time-dependent perturbations as

$$\beta_0(z, t) = \beta_0(z, T) + \Delta\beta_0(z, t), \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{\beta}(z, t) = \vec{\beta}(z, T) + \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t). \quad (5)$$

Over the t time scale, we may assume T as a fixed parameter. We may then decompose \mathbf{U} as [6, 7]

$$\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U}_T \mathbf{U}_t, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{U}_T = \exp \left[-\frac{i}{2} \varphi_0(T) \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \vec{\varphi}(T) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right]. \quad (7)$$

The quasi static propagation changes described by $\varphi_0(T)$ and $\vec{\varphi}(T)$ are in general large because they include those induced by the static polarization averaged wavevector and by the static birefringence over the entire link length. The matrix \mathbf{U}_T is the solution of

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}_T}{dz} = -\frac{i}{2} \left[\beta_0(z, T) \mathbb{1} + \vec{\beta}(z, T) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right] \mathbf{U}_T, \quad (8)$$

with initial condition $\mathbf{U}_T = \mathbb{1}$ at $z = 0$. Differentiating Eq. (6) with respect to z and using Eq. (3) we obtain

$$\mathbf{U}_T \frac{d\mathbf{U}_t}{dz} = -\frac{i}{2} \left[\Delta\beta_0(z, t) \mathbb{1} + \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right] \mathbf{U}_T \mathbf{U}_t, \quad (9)$$

that yields

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}_t}{dz} = -\frac{i}{2} \left[\Delta\beta_0(z, t) \mathbb{1} + \mathbf{U}_T^\dagger \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \mathbf{U}_T \right] \mathbf{U}_t. \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_T^\dagger = \mathbf{U}_T^{-1}$ is the hermitian conjugate and also the inverse of the unitary matrix \mathbf{U}_T . If we define $\mathbf{R} = \exp[\vec{\varphi}(z, T) \times]$ as the operator representing a rotation in the three-dimensional Stokes space by an angle $\varphi(T) = |\vec{\varphi}(z, T)|$ around the axis $\vec{\varphi}(z, T) / \varphi(z, T)$, then we have [6]

$$\mathbf{U}_T^{-1} \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \mathbf{U}_T = \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t) \cdot \mathbf{R} \vec{\sigma} = \mathbf{R}^{-1} \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t) \cdot \vec{\sigma}, \quad (11)$$

so that Eq. (10) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}_t}{dz} = -\frac{i}{2} \left[\Delta\beta_0(z, t) \mathbb{1} + \Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right] \mathbf{U}_t. \quad (12)$$

where $\Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t) = \exp[-\vec{\varphi}(z, T) \times] \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ is the birefringence vector at position z in a frame rotating with the quasi-static birefringence averaged over T_{win} . Having removed the “free” evolution of the polarization along the fiber (produced by the quasi static birefringence), this approach is similar to the use of the interaction representation in quantum mechanics [8]. Since the birefringence $\vec{\beta}(z, T)$ includes the static fiber birefringence, whose correlation length is of the order of tens of meters, we may assume that the direction of $\Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ is fully randomized by \mathbf{R} and that $\Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t)$ is fully isotropic. The matrix \mathbf{U}_t can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{U}_t = \exp \left[-\frac{i}{2} \Delta\varphi_0(t) \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \Delta\vec{\varphi}(t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right], \quad (13)$$

Left-multiplying by \mathbf{U}_T^\dagger both sides of (6) yields

$$\mathbf{U}_t = \mathbf{U}_T^\dagger \mathbf{U}, \quad (14)$$

which gives a method to calculate \mathbf{U}_t once \mathbf{U}_T and \mathbf{U} are known. Singular value decomposition applied to the transmission matrix extracted from the receiver provides \mathbf{U} . Expressing \mathbf{U} as in Eq. (1), the common phase can in principle be computed by

$$\varphi_0 = i \text{trace} [\ln(\mathbf{U})], \quad (15)$$

and the components φ_k of the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}$ by

$$\varphi_k = i \text{trace} [\ln(\mathbf{U}) \sigma_k]. \quad (16)$$

A more efficient way of computing these quantities is presented in the appendix. After the evaluation of φ_0 and $\vec{\varphi}$, the matrices \mathbf{U} must be regularized to correct for the sign ambiguity arising from the fact that \mathbf{U} and $-\mathbf{U}$ correspond to a phase φ_0 different by 2π . A 2π difference characterizes values belonging to different branches of the multi-valued logarithm in Eq. (15). The inherent ambiguity arising from the fact the all numerical algorithms implementing Eqs. (15) return the principal value of the logarithm, implies that the matrices \mathbf{U} after the separation of the polarization averaged phase are generally discontinuous in time because of sign changes. Of course this fact does not affect polarization because \mathbf{U} and $-\mathbf{U}$ describe the same polarization transformation, but does produce jumps in the rotation vector from $\vec{\varphi}$ to $\vec{\varphi} + 2\pi(\vec{\varphi}/\varphi)$ that must be corrected. An efficient algorithm for this purpose is presented in the appendix.

After regularization, the matrix \mathbf{U}_T can then be evaluated by averaging over a suitably long time window T_{win} the matrix \mathbf{U} and specifically, to preserve the unitary nature of the matrix in the averaging process, by calculating the time-averaged polarization averaged phase $\mathbb{E}_{T_{\text{win}}}(\varphi_0)$ and the time-averaged rotation vector $\mathbb{E}_{T_{\text{win}}}(\vec{\varphi})$. This gives to the matrix \mathbf{U}_t given by Eq. (14) the expression

$$\mathbf{U}_t = \exp \left[-\frac{i}{2} \mathbb{E}_{T_{\text{win}}}(\varphi_0) \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \mathbb{E}_{T_{\text{win}}}(\vec{\varphi}) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right] \exp \left[-\frac{i}{2} \varphi_0(t) \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \vec{\varphi}(t) \cdot \vec{\sigma} \right]. \quad (17)$$

Notice that Eq. (17) shows that the matrix \mathbf{U}_t has the meaning of the Jones matrix of the link post compensated with respect to the slowly varying and the static propagation changes. The pre-compensated Jones matrix can also be calculated by defining $\mathbf{U} = (\mathbf{U}_t)_{\text{pre}} \mathbf{U}_T$, hence by using $(\mathbf{U}_t)_{\text{pre}} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{U}_T^{-1}$. Using Eq. (6) it is immediate to show that the relation with the post-compensated matrix is $(\mathbf{U}_t)_{\text{pre}} = \mathbf{U}_T \mathbf{U}_t \mathbf{U}_T^{-1}$, and hence

the corresponding pre-compensated $\Delta\vec{\varphi}_{\text{pre}}$ differs from $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ only for a proper rotation. The advantage of the use of the post-compensated Jones matrix lies in the fact that the compensation is achieved by rotating the output polarization states without altering the input polarization states. With this choice, one can trace back the fluctuations of the components of the rotation vector to specific input polarizations.

The equation describing the evolution of \mathbf{U}_t at longitudinal position z along the fiber is Eq. (12) where we recall that $\Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t)$ is the birefringence vector at position z rotated by the quasi-static birefringence averaged over T_{win} . Then, if we expand the exponent in Eq. (13) with $L = z$ to first order, which is legitimate because the birefringence fluctuations in the rotating frame are small, we obtain

$$\mathbf{U}_t \simeq \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \Delta\varphi_0 \mathbb{1} - \frac{i}{2} \Delta\vec{\varphi} \cdot \vec{\sigma}. \quad (18)$$

Entering Eq. (18) into Eq. (13) taking the terms of the same order and using that $\Delta\beta_0$ and $\Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ are of the same order of $\Delta\varphi_0$ and $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$, we obtain

$$\frac{d\Delta\varphi_0}{dz} = \Delta\beta_0(z, t), \quad (19)$$

and

$$\frac{d\Delta\vec{\varphi}}{dz} = \Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t), \quad (20)$$

so that, after integrating up to the cable length $z = L$, we finally obtain

$$\Delta\varphi_0 = \int_0^L dz \Delta\beta_0(z, t), \quad (21)$$

and

$$\Delta\vec{\varphi} = \int_0^L dz \Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t). \quad (22)$$

The use of the polarization averaged phase of Eq. (21) for sensing is hampered by the high sensitivity of phase to perturbations, which produces frequent phase jumps limiting the usable linear range, and because the accuracy of phase estimation is limited by the fact that phase retrieval is coupled to polarization retrieval [5]. We therefore concentrate on polarization in the following analysis.

The above analysis shows that the measurement of $\Delta\vec{\varphi}(L, t)$ in the rotating frame allows the determination of $\int_0^L dz \Delta\vec{\beta}_R(z, t)$, in turn proportional to the integrated hydrostatic pressure modulation [3]. It is worth noting that, conversely, a direct spectral analysis of the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}$ as defined in Eq. (1), or of its perturbations, does not return the same quantity, because in general $\exp\{[\vec{\varphi}(T) + \Delta\vec{\varphi}(t)] \cdot \vec{\sigma}\} \neq \exp[\vec{\varphi}(T) \cdot \vec{\sigma}] \exp[\Delta\vec{\varphi}(t) \cdot \vec{\sigma}]$.

It was shown in [3] that the analysis of the Stokes vector corresponding to a fixed input state \vec{s}_0 , as done in [2, 3], allows the determination of the components of $\int_0^L dz \Delta\vec{\beta}(z, t)$ orthogonal to the input state \vec{s}_0 only. Being the fluctuations of the rotation vector over a sufficiently long time isotropic (a condition that has been verified to be valid in most cases using the experimental data), we obtain that the fluctuations of the Stokes vector with a fixed input polarization $\langle \Delta s^2 \rangle$ and the fluctuations of the rotation vector are related by $\langle \Delta \varphi^2 \rangle = (3/2) \langle \Delta s^2 \rangle$. It was shown in ref. [3] that the main contribution to the birefringence fluctuations comes from the fluctuations of the hydrostatic pressure of the seawater through the Poisson effect (see the analysis in [4, 9] for details). Using then Eq. (19) of ref. [3],

$$\langle \Delta s^2 \rangle = \frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda} \right)^2 \kappa^2 \epsilon_P^2 \int_0^L \Delta P^2 dz, \quad (23)$$

we obtain for $\Delta\varphi^2$ averaged over the longitudinal birefringence fluctuations the expression

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Delta\varphi^2 \rangle &= \frac{3}{8} \pi \left(\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda} \right)^2 \kappa^2 \epsilon_p^2 \int_0^L \Delta P^2 dz \\ &\simeq \frac{3}{8} \pi \left(\frac{2\pi c}{\lambda} \right)^2 \kappa^2 \epsilon_p^2 \Delta P^2 L_{\text{int}}, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $\kappa^2 = \langle \tau \rangle^2 / z$ is the polarization mode dispersion (PMD) coefficient squared [6], usually expressed in ps^2/km , c is the speed of light in vacuum, and λ is the wavelength. Here, following ref. [3] we have assumed proportionality between the hydrodynamic pressure induced strain ϵ and the pressure modulation ΔP , that is $\epsilon = \epsilon_p \Delta P$. In the second approximate equality, we assumed that the pressure change is experienced over an interaction length L_{int} .

It is worth emphasizing that due to the spatially incoherent nature of the detection, the polarization signal does not average out positive and negative strain regions produced by perturbations that travel at the speed of seismic waves [3]. If sensing were performed with an ultra-narrow linewidth laser as in [10, 11], the signal would be reduced and possibly even canceled by the averaging of the positive and negative strain regions.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

We applied the theory on the transmission matrices extracted with a sampling period $T_s = 0.5$ s from the Infinera (now Nokia) transceivers of the sections of the Sparkle's MedNautilus undersea fiber-optic system connecting Catania to Haifa and Catania to Tel Aviv (see Fig. 1). The monitoring period extended over four days starting from 10:18:51 UTC of May 30, 2025. We obtained the Jones matrices by taking the unitary part of the singular-value decomposition applied to the extracted transmission matrices. Next, we extracted the perturbations of the rotation matrix with the procedure described in Sec. 2. Finally, we computed the spectrograms of the three components of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ utilizing a short time Fourier transform that uses a Hamming window of length $N_{\text{win}} = 2^{10}$ samples of $T_s = 0.5$ s duration, with $N_{\text{over}} = 2^9$ samples of overlap between adjoining temporal segments. The result of this procedure applied to the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link is shown in Fig. 2. The horizontal lines that appear in the low frequency portion of the spectrogram of the first component $\Delta\varphi_1$ below 50 mHz are artifacts of phase recovery algorithm, that couples the retrieval of the phase with the retrieval of the first component of the rotation vector [5]. Adding up the spectrograms of the three components of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ for the case of Fig. 2, we obtain the spectrogram shown in Fig. 3. The enhanced contrast resulting from the addition of the three spectrograms permits an easy identification of the signature of the earthquake of magnitude $M_w = 5.8$ occurring on June 2, 2025. This appears as a vertical line in the spectrogram, highlighted with an oval in the figure. Fig. 4 presents a zoom of the spectrogram of Fig. 3 from three hours before to three hours after the earthquake, showing that the spectral content of the perturbation extends down to approximately 40 mHz. Unlike the others, this spectrogram was obtained using a Hamming window of length $N_{\text{win}} = 2^9$ samples, with an overlap of $N_{\text{over}} = 2^9 - 1$ samples.

The rationale behind the addition of the spectrograms of the three components is the following. The spectrograms of Fig. 3 are the square modulus of the short-time Fourier transform of the temporal sequence of each component, but they are also

Fig. 2. Spectrograms of the three components of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link. In this and in the other figures the zero of the time scale is set to the earthquake time 23:17:28 UTC.

equal to the Fourier transform of the short-time autocorrelation function of the same sequence. Consequently, the sum of the three spectrograms is equal to the Fourier transform of the short-time *vector* autocorrelation function, obtained as the scalar product between the perturbations of the rotation vector and its delayed replicas. This identification shows that the sum of the three spectrograms is an intrinsic geometrical property of the rotation vector, independent of the reference frame. In particular, it is invariant for both proper and improper¹ rotations of Stokes space and, in particular, is the same for pre- and post-compensated Jones matrices. Being the perturbations of the rotation vector isotropic, this spectrogram fully characterizes the vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$. For this reason, we consider it appropriate to refer to the sum of the spectrograms of the three components of $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ as the spectrogram of $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$, and we will adopt this convention hereafter. In addition, we will refrain from showing the spectrograms of the three components separately and present only the spectrograms of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$.

Figure 5 shows the spectrogram of $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ obtained using the Jones matrix extracted from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link. The spectrograms in Figs. 3 and 5 exhibit the same features, despite the fact that the bidirectional Catania–Haifa link operates with a pair of fibers that, while sharing the same cable, are physically distinct. This is indicative of the fact that these features are caused by processes occurring in the deep sea and not in the transceivers. More importantly, it demonstrates that the random spatial distribution of birefringence—different for the two fibers—is effectively self-averaged, so that the random nature of the spatial fluctuations of the birefringence does not compromise the accuracy of the detection. Notice that the opposite propagation direction on the two fibers does not affect the spectrograms. This is because the Jones matrix of the backward propagation is the transpose of that of the forward. Since the rotation vectors of a Jones matrix and its transpose are related by the inversion of the third coordinate—hence by an improper rotation—the vector autocorrelation functions for forward and backward propagation are identical, as are the corresponding spectrograms [12].

Figures 6 and 7 show the spectrograms of the perturbations

¹We recall that an improper rotation can always be decomposed into a proper rotation followed by an inversion of an axis.

Fig. 3. Spectrogram of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link. The spectrogram is Fourier transform of the short-time vector autocorrelation function of $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$, and is obtained by adding the spectrograms of the three components of $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ shown in Fig 2. The oval highlights the earthquake signature.

Fig. 4. Zoom of the spectrogram of Fig. 3 around the earthquake time.

Fig. 5. Spectrogram of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link. The oval highlights the earthquake signature.

Fig. 6. Spectrogram of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Tel Aviv terminal of the Catania–Tel Aviv link. The oval highlights the earthquake signature.

of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the two fibers of the Catania–Tel Aviv link, from the Tel Aviv and Catania terminals respectively. Also in this case the similarity of the features displayed by the two spectrograms is evident and the signature of the earthquake is also clearly visible, although it is weaker because of the larger distance of the cable from the earthquake epicenter. All spectrograms display sharp resonances in the range between 200 to 500 mHz compatible with acoustic excitations triggered by solid tides. In the spectrograms of Figs. 6 and 7 are also evident excitations in the secondary microseism band, from 80 to 160 mHz, possibly generated by Rayleigh wave excitations. These excitations are visible on the Catania–Tel Aviv link but not on the Catania–Haifa link. This difference is likely due to the peculiar characteristics of the Catania–Tel Aviv link, which runs in front of the Nile Delta and, having been installed 25 years ago, is probably completely buried in sediments. As a result, this link is particularly sensitive to resonances of the thick sediment layer beneath it. The Catania–Haifa link, by contrast, runs further north. Although it is also deployed in a sediment-rich region, it is more strongly coupled to the seawater than to the sediment layer, thinner in that area than in the Nile Delta region.

A more quantitative analysis of the earthquake characteristics

can be gained from the analysis of the temporal traces of the three components of the perturbations of the rotation vector, and their length squared. Figure 8 shows the temporal traces of the three components and of the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025. It is evident that it is very difficult to identify the signature of an earthquake from these traces. Figure 9 shows the temporal traces of the three components and of the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025, after processing. The traces are high-pass filtered above 50 mHz. The zero of the time scale is set to the earthquake time 23:17:28 UTC. The traces extracted from the Catania terminal of the same link are reported in Fig. 10. A green vertical line indicates the arrival time of the perturbations caused by the earthquake, $\Delta t_1 = 30$ s, which has been estimated by simple visual inspection. Being the optical cable sensitive to the pressure modulation via the Poisson effect, the traces are caused by the components of the P-waves generated by the earthquake orthogonal to the seafloor that produce a pressure modulation eventually revealed by the cable. The depth of the hypocenter was $D = 72$ km according to the USGC catalog [13] and $D = 68$ according to the INGV catalog [14], and the distance of the epicenter to the closest point of the Catania–

Fig. 7. Spectrogram of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Tel Aviv link. The oval highlights the earthquake signature.

342 Haifa cable is $d_0 = 110$ km. This implies a P-wave speed of
 343 $v = \sqrt{d_0^2 + D^2} / \Delta t_1 \simeq 4.38$ km/s for USGC and $v \simeq 4.31$ for
 344 INGV.

Fig. 8. Temporal traces of the three components and the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025, without processing.

345 Figures 11 and 12 show the temporal traces high-pass filtered
 346 above 500 mHz of the three components and the length squared
 347 of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the
 348 Tel Aviv and the Catania terminals of the Catania–Tel Aviv link,
 349 respectively, again from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025. In this
 350 case, the temporal traces are filtered above 500 mHz instead of 50
 351 mHz to reject the noise caused by the acoustic wave resonances
 352 present in the Catania–Tel Aviv link and not in the Catania–Haifa
 353 link. Also in this case, the zero of the time scale is set to the
 354 earthquake time 23:17:28 UTC. The green vertical line indicates
 355 the arrival time of the perturbations caused by the earthquake,
 356 $\Delta t_2 = 116$ s. The distance of the epicenter to the closest point of
 357 the Catania–Tel Aviv cable is $d'_0 = 535$ km. The estimated speed
 358 of the P-wave is $v' = \sqrt{d_0'^2 + D^2} / \Delta t_2 \simeq 4.65$ km/s for both
 359 USGS and INGV. The arrival times to both cables are consistent
 360 with a P-wave speed of the order of 4.65 km/s. This relatively
 361 low value can be justified by the sediment-rich Mediterranean
 362 crust in the region of the earthquake.

Fig. 9. Temporal traces of the three components and the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Haifa terminal of the Catania–Haifa link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025, high-pass filtered above 50 mHz. The green vertical line indicates the arrival time of the perturbation, $\Delta t_1 = 30$ s.

4. CONCLUSIONS

363 We have developed and validated a general theoretical frame-
 364 work for interpreting the time-dependent polarization changes
 365 in optical fibers affected by random polarization coupling. Our
 366 results demonstrate that the Jones matrix retrieved by coherent
 367 receivers operating under standard telecommunication condi-
 368 tions contains complete and usable information about the exter-
 369 nal perturbations, including seismic events, and can therefore be
 370 used for geophysical sensing. By analyzing counter-propagating
 371 signals in fibers within the same cable, we showed that the
 372 sensing information is robust against the effects of random po-
 373 larization coupling. Applying this method to the Sparkle’s Med-
 374 Nautilus undersea fiber-optic link, we successfully detected and
 375 characterized the seismic event of June 2, 2025, using live traffic
 376 data from commercial transponders. These findings confirm the
 377 feasibility of passive seismic monitoring using existing subma-
 378 rine telecommunication infrastructure, with no need for dedi-
 379 cated sensors or interruptions to service. This approach opens
 380 the door to large-scale geophysical monitoring using global op-
 381 tical networks.
 382

A. THE NUMERICAL ALGORITHM

383 The procedure described in the main text is not optimized for
 384 computational efficiency. In this appendix, we detail a more
 385 efficient way of calculating the perturbation of the rotation vector.
 386 We also provide an efficient and reliable algorithm to ensure the
 387 continuity of the rotation vector.

388 The Jones matrix \mathbf{U} is first obtained by singular value decom-
 389 position of the transmission matrix extracted from the receiver.
 390 Then, after computing the common phase as

$$\varphi_0 = i \log[\det(\mathbf{U})], \quad (25)$$

392 where with $\log(\cdot)$ we denote the principal value of the logarithm,
 393 the polarization averaged phase φ_0 can be subtracted using

$$\mathbf{U}' = \exp(i\varphi_0/2) \mathbf{U}, \quad (26)$$

394 obtaining a SU(2) matrix (a unitary matrix with determinant
 395 equal to one). Being a simple scalar, the polarization averaged

Fig. 10. Temporal traces of the three components and the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Haifa link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025, high-pass filtered above 50 mHz. The green vertical line indicates the arrival time of the perturbation, $\Delta t_1 = 30$ s.

Fig. 11. Temporal traces of the three components and the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Tel Aviv terminal of the Catania–Tel Aviv link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025, high-pass filtered above 500 mHz. The green vertical line indicates the arrival time of the perturbation, $\Delta t_2 = 116$ s.

396 phase is decoupled from polarization and, from this point on, 419
397 can be easily processed separately. Consequently, in the follow- 420
398 ing analysis, we dump it and consider only the polarization- 421
399 dependent part \mathbf{U}' of the matrix \mathbf{U} . The elements of an $\text{SU}(2)$ 422
400 matrix \mathbf{U}' admit the Cayley–Klein parametrization [6] 423

$$\mathbf{U}' = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ -\beta^* & \alpha^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

401 with $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$. We then expand \mathbf{U}' in terms of the Pauli 424
402 matrices given in Eq. (2) 425

$$\mathbf{U}' = q_0 \mathbb{1} - \vec{q} \cdot \vec{\sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} q_0 - iq_1 & -q_3 - iq_2 \\ q_3 - iq_2 & q_0 + iq_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (28)$$

403 where $\vec{q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3)$. The value of q_0 and of the components of 426
404 \vec{q} are immediately obtained from the elements of the first row of 427
405 \mathbf{U}' using 428

$$q_0 = \text{real}(\alpha), \quad (29)$$

$$q_1 = -\text{imag}(\alpha), \quad (30)$$

$$q_2 = -\text{imag}(\beta), \quad (31)$$

$$q_3 = -\text{real}(\beta). \quad (32)$$

406 If we define $\vec{Q} = (q_0, \vec{q})$, we have $\vec{Q} \cdot \vec{Q} = 1$. Being the matrix 430
407 vectors $[q_0 \mathbb{1}, -iq_1 \sigma_1, -iq_2 \sigma_2, -iq_3 \sigma_3]$ isomorphic to quaternions 431
408 [15], the vector \vec{Q} represents the unit quaternion associated with 432
409 the three-dimensional rotation associated to the $\text{SU}(2)$ matrix \mathbf{U}' . 433

410 Equation (28) shows that a change of sign of \mathbf{U}' changes also 434
411 the sign of q_0 and \vec{q} and hence of \vec{Q} . The representation of \mathbf{U}' 435
412 in terms of \vec{Q} is therefore very useful to regularize the matrix- 436
413 ces \mathbf{U}' by removing the sign ambiguity that arises from the fact 437
414 that, as described in the main text, the matrices obtained after 438
415 the removal of the polarization averaged phase are in general 439
416 discontinuous because of sign changes. This can be done very 440
417 conveniently by flipping the sign of $\vec{Q}(t + \Delta t)$ whenever the 441
418 scalar product of two consecutive vectors, $\vec{Q}(t) \cdot \vec{Q}(t + \Delta t)$, is 442

419 negative. This choice ensures that successive quaternions fol- 420
421 lows the shortest geodesic path on the unit hyper-sphere, thus 421
422 avoiding artificial discontinuity of the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}$. This 422
423 strategy is more direct and accurate than imposing the continuity 423
424 of the rotation vector directly because \mathbf{U}' depends linearly 424
425 on \vec{Q} and nonlinearly on $\vec{\varphi}$. 425

426 After regularization of the vector \vec{Q} , we compute the rotation 426
427 vector as follows. Comparison of Eq. (28) with the expansion [6]

$$\mathbf{U}' = \cos(\varphi/2) \mathbb{1} - i\hat{\varphi} \cdot \vec{\sigma} \sin(\varphi/2), \quad (33)$$

427 where $\hat{\varphi} = \vec{\varphi}/\varphi$, shows right away that

$$q_0 = \cos(\varphi/2), \quad (34)$$

$$\vec{q} = \hat{\varphi} \sin(\varphi/2). \quad (35)$$

428 These expressions can be readily inverted to give the rotation 429
429 vector $\vec{\varphi}$ as

$$\vec{\varphi} = \frac{2 \arccos(q_0)}{\sqrt{1 - q_0^2}} \vec{q} = 2 \arccos(q_0) \hat{q}, \quad (36)$$

430 where $\hat{q} = |\vec{q}|$ and in the last equality we have used that 431
431 $\vec{q} \cdot \vec{q} = 1 - q_0^2$. After using Eqs. (36) over the regularized com- 432
432 ponents of \vec{Q} , we then proceed as described in the main text: 433
433 we calculate $\mathbb{E}_{T_{\text{win}}}(\vec{\varphi})$, that is, we average the rotation vector $\vec{\varphi}$ 434
434 over the window time T_{win} , and compute the matrix \mathbf{U}'_t (the 435
435 prime is because we consider the polarization-dependent part 436
436 only) by compensating for the average rotation using Eq. (17) 437
437 with $\varphi_0 = 0$. Once the compensated matrix \mathbf{U}'_t is obtained, 438
438 the procedure is repeated by computing the components of the 439
439 unit quaternion associated to this matrix, compensating for dis- 440
440 continuities enforcing the positiveness of the scalar products 441
441 between successive quaternions, and evaluating from the regu- 442
442 larized quaternions the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ associated to the 443
443 compensated Jones matrix \mathbf{U}_t . It is worth reminding here that 444
444 quaternions are only an intermediate of the processing whereas 445
445 $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ is the quantity of interest for sensing, because it is equal to 446
446 the spatially integrated perturbations of the birefringence vector 447
447 (see Eq. (22)), in turn proportional to the spatially integrated 448
448 pressure modulation applied to the fiber.

Fig. 12. Temporal traces of the three components and the length squared of the perturbations of the rotation vector $\Delta\vec{\varphi}$ extracted from the Catania terminal of the Catania–Tel Aviv link from 23:10:00 to 23:30 of June 2, 2025, high-pass filtered above 500 mHz. The green vertical line indicates the arrival time of the perturbation, $\Delta t_2 = 116$ s.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper will be available in a public repository of Project Zenodo (ecstatic@modus.ltd).

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